

Developing hi-tech glasshouses in Angus and Dundee

An outline feasibility study

Introduction

The case for capitalising on the advances in controlled environment agriculture (CEA) to develop the concept of modern fresh produce production for high value produce such as tomatoes etc, in the Tay Cities region is explored here. Note that this is a preliminary exploration of the territory and not a feasibility study. Rather this sets the scene for the fuller development of the concept, the derisking of the idea and the identification of key areas that need explored and add credibility to the concept.

Much of the information within this is drawn from conversations with stakeholders. We are grateful for the time they have taken to provide information and to outline/show their facilities.

Professor Derek Stewart,
Director of the Advanced Plant Growth
Centre
The James Hutton Institute

Peter Richie
Nourish Scotland

Executive summary

- Michelin Scotland Innovation Parc (MSIP) offers a promising site for the development of up to 7 ha of controlled environment agriculture systems, predominantly glasshouse-based system with possible a vertical farm. The latter would be used to grow existing fresh produce and plant stock (plantlets) to replace suboptimal imports and exploitation in local field/polytunnel/glasshouse production. There also exists a steel-framed shed which may offer potential for conversion to a glasshouse or as a specific site for a new build CEA system (glasshouse and/or vertical farm) following demolition of the existing shed.
- Initial exploration of the surrounding environment and existing neighbour agreements suggest that the MVV plant can supply sufficient energy in various forms to support production.
- The market for tomatoes (and other high value fresh produce) is growing, and the UK/Scotland meets most of its demand through imports (though a number of other large-scale developments using renewable energy are coming on stream in England).
- A partnership between various public and commercial actors could be the best way to take the project forward. This site could provide a proof of concept for a wider renaissance of Scotland's glasshouse sector.
- Many variables affect the viability of the project and these need to be explored in more depth.

Contents

1. Why invest in hi-tech glasshouse production?
2. Key requirements for success
3. Potential locations in Angus and Dundee
4. Possible business model
5. Possible add-ons
6. Known unknowns
7. A budget with gaps
8. Next steps

1 Why invest in glasshouse production?

The UK has an annual £6Bn deficit on fruit and vegetables. The value of home-produced vegetables and fruit amounts to just under £1.8Bn and just under £1Bn billion, respectively¹. However, horticulture used less than 1% of UK agricultural land in 2018, and in the context of UK agriculture, the horticulture sector is comparably high value, constituting 20% of production value. A significant portion of this can be classified as protected cropping, here an encompassing term for polytunnels, glasshouse production etc and broadly considered to be Controlled Environment Agriculture (CEA). At a Scottish level the data on the latest data from the Scottish Agricultural census (June 2023)² identifies the hectareage and trends (Table 1) in a limited number of protected crop but no associated market values (see below for data from The Knowledge Bank, Scotland food and Drink). The trends for the identified fresh produce identify the dominance of strawberry and the possibly the limitations of current Scottish fresh produce focus and little feel for the potential for other crops (herbs, exotics and protein crops). In addition, the sourcing of plantlets for production, a major cost for fresh produce production in CEA and open field, remains a problem for the industry with imported plant stock suffering from the following problems:

- Strawberry yields vary 167g-700g per plant, with averages around 500g, (>500g is required for profit).
- Quality varies ~30% plant death (c.£12M value), ~40% have root pathogens, requiring chemical inputs at replanting.
- Time to fruit production on bush and cane crops significantly reduce profitability.
- Aren't optimised for the UK planting schedules and not always available when required.
- Imported plants/canes are mainly dormant cold-stored plan.

At the UK level the analogous data from Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (DEFRA, 2023)³ is highlights a significantly different scenario with much more significant levels of CEA activity but crucially identifying significant opportunities to on-shore production in crops such as soft fruit (30-40% imported, ~100kTonnes, ~£300M), and tomatoes/cucumbers/lettuce/sweet peppers etc totalling 1124kTonne (£295M) of home production against imports of ~1MTonnes/£1.5Bn.

At the Scottish shopping basket level data from the The Knowledge Bank⁴ identifies that fruit and vegetable purchases are steady and just behind dairy and bread in terms of purchase frequency (Fig 1.) and that (at a UK level) fresh produce dominate purchases over frozen (Fig. 2.) with the value for fresh produce identified as £10.6Bn.

¹ Ornamental Horticulture and Roundtable Group (2021). Unlocking green growth: A plan from the ornamental horticulture & landscaping industry.; Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs et al. (2022). Latest horticulture statistics – Horticulture statistics - 2021. UK Government.

² Scottish Agricultural Census: June 2023.

<https://www.gov.scot/binaries/content/documents/govscot/publications/statistics/2023/10/results-scottish-agricultural-census-june-2023/documents/agricultural-census-june-2023-tables/agricultural-census-june-2023-tables/govscot%3Adocument/June%2BAgricultural%2BCensus%2B2023%2BTables%2B.xlsx>

³ DEFAR Horticultural Statistics 2023. <https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/latest-horticulture-statistics>

⁴ Produce Deep Dive Report: GB Retail (2023) The Knowledge Bank, Scotland Food and Drink.

<https://theknowledgebank.scot/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/vegetable-accompaniments-deep-dive-report-january-2022-web-version.pdf>

Fig. 1. Frequency of purchasing different types of food and drink for in-home consumption during the past 6 months (Produce Deep Dive Report: GB Retail (2023) The Knowledge Bank, Scotland Food and Drink).

Fig. 2. Value of Frozen Versus Fresh Fruit & Veg (£bn), 52 w/e 01 July 2023
Adding support to the concept of sustainable production, here via local production with allied reduced travel miles (and associated emissions), is the survey data by the Knowledge Bank (2023) which identified (Fig.3.) provenance is a strong driver of purchase with Scottish produce preferred.

Fig. 3. Products they are more likely to buy if they are made in Scotland (The Knowledge Bank, 2023).

The survey further highlighted that improving availability (here via controlled environment agriculture production systems facilitating year-round production) gave indication that there was an increased likelihood to buy more produces (Fig. 4.)

Fig. 4. Scottish products would like to be able to buy more often. (The Knowledge Bank, 2023).

The driver behind consumer purchase were further mined and identified criteria such as taste, freshness, local produce/ingredients, low carbon footprint. Of these taste and place rank highest. Further granularity here is needed, especially in terms of monetising these drivers and also addressing the knowledge gaps around the produce for ingredients (secondary food production) and the potential for exports.

The recent UK Parliament article “Future of Horticulture (contributed to by D Stewart, JHI)⁵ identified that:

- The UK’s production of vegetables decreased by 5.8% to 2.4 million tonnes
- Protected vegetable production (grown in a protected environment, such as a glasshouse or polythene tunnel) fell by 5.7% to 247 thousand tonnes — the seventh consecutive year of falling production since the 2015 peak production of 310 thousand tonnes
- Land area used for protected vegetable production fell by 11% Vegetable imports increased by 3.3% to over 2 million tonnes
- The sector faces multiple challenges arising from high energy costs, low profit margins, trade barriers and a dependency on migrant labour, while also mitigating the implications of climate change.
- As an example of the impacts of energy cost raises Glasshouse growers have operated in the Lea Valley, a 450-acre area north of London, for over 100 years. This land accounts for around 65% of the UK’s cucumber and pepper production, as well as tomato and aubergine production. However, approximately 50% of growers in the Lea Valley Growers Association could not plant crops in 2022 due to high energy costs.

⁵ Wentworth and Bradshaw (2023). Future of Horticulture. UK Parliament. <https://post.parliament.uk/research-briefings/post-pn-0707/#:~:text=Technological%20innovation%20could%20help%20to,and%20AI%20mediated%20crop%20monitoring.>

These discussion on the changes need in our food production were mirrored in a recent review (yet to be released) by the Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs on CEA and its place in a net-zero future. This review took a serious and deep dive into the decarbonisation of CEA and identified how central energy was either as heating/cooling, humidity control, lighting etc. This identified the following:

- An estimated 26% of all direct energy use in UK agriculture goes to protected crops overall, and 15% to protected edibles, while protected edibles make up only a small fraction of total food production in the UK.
- Total energy consumption of the agricultural sector in 2015 in the UK was 117 thousand TJ at an energy intensity of 9.8 TJ per £m of value added.
- Energy costs were in the past up to 30% of the overall variable production costs in CEA, and with recent price shifts in the cost of gas this is increasing dramatically.

This identifies that CAE products need to explore multiple options to maximise energy efficiency AND wherever possible develop relationships with providers of energy to reduce basal energy costs.

All of the issues above arguably coalesce at MSIP in terms of the following:

- Site and available footprint (either reconditioning the existing building or new build)
- Existing energy provision via steam and electricity
- Preliminary identified interested offtakers for all/mist produce.
- Preliminary identified interested partners to run the proposed opportunity for fresh produce and plantlets production.
- The Advanced Plant Growth Centre, a £27M Tay Cities Deal, hosted at The James Hutton institute, experiences in CEA including vertical farming, and both willing and able to manage the journey to full economic development.

Table 1. Scottish Agricultural census (June 2023) identifying protected cropping crop data and trends.

Vegetables and fruits for human consumption	2012 Area (Hectares)	2013 Area (Hectares)	2014 Area (Hectares)	2015 Area (Hectares)	2016 Area (Hectares)	2017 Area (Hectares)	2018 Area (Hectares)	2019 Area (Hectares)	2020 Area (Hectares)	2021 Area (Hectares)	2022 Area (Hectares)	2023 Area (Hectares)	5 year average 2017 to 2021 (Hectares)	% Change 2023 to 5 year average
Tomatoes grown under cover	3	3	3	3	2	3	3	3	3	2	[f]	1	3	-80.1%
Strawberries grown under cover	699	771	818	916	920	981	1,106	1,100	1,165	1,151	[f]	992	1,101	-9.9%
Raspberries grown under cover	186	175	188	203	199	172	162	165	169	152	[f]	131	164	-20.0%
Blueberries grown under cover	x	x	27	85	115	159	189	205	239	226	[f]	220	203	8.0%
Other fruit grown under cover	38	36	42	5	39	34	34	22	35	35	[f]	18	32	-41.9%
Vegetables grown under cover	11	12	9	9	10	20	14	12	23	17	[f]	3	17	-80.4%
Bedding and pot plants grown under cover	23	17	16	15	14	14	17	19	18	14	[f]	9	17	-47.0%
Hardy Nursery Stock grown under cover	13	15	14	16	12	21	14	24	21	21	[f]	9	20	-54.1%
Unused area grown under cover	x	x	x	20	23	11	14	5	4	6	[f]	27	8	243.5%
Total plastic and glass clad structures	1,039	1,038	1,121	1,271	1,332	1,415	1,547	1,555	1,669	1,622	[f]	1,412	1,562	-9.6%
Strawberries grown in open/under cover	885	911	913	939	993	1,058	1,133	1,132	1,194	1,187	[f]	1,015	1,141	-11.0%
Raspberries grown in open/under cover	391	361	311	351	326	299	271	254	241	243	[f]	200	262	-23.7%
Blackcurrants grown in open/under cover	276	295	308	314	302	321	279	270	297	320	[f]	381	298	28.0%

Blueberries grown in open/under cover	x	x	45	120	132	183	219	235	265	253	[f]	241	231	4.3%
Tomatoes grown in open/under cover	3	3	3	3	2	3	3	3	3	2	[f]	1	3	-80.1%
Other fruit grown in open/under cover	180	198	166	81	122	200	152	143	172	157	[f]	124	165	-24.8%
Total soft fruit	1,734	1,769	1,746	1,809	1,878	2,064	2,057	2,037	2,172	2,161	[f]	1,961	2,098	-6.5%
Walk in plastic structures (i.e. polytunnel)	1,000	1,004	1,078	1,233	1,295	1,376	1,512	1,497	1,633	1,590	[f]	1,321	1,522	-13.2%
Glass clad structures (i.e. glasshouse)	39	34	42	38	37	39	35	57	36	32	[f]	90	40	126.2%

[f] - data to follow

Supporting information

Health and taste

Tomatoes and other warm weather crops such as sweet peppers, cucumbers and aubergines are part of your five a day. Such produce contain a plethora of nutrients and health beneficial components all of which, as a regular part of the diet, have been identified as reducing the risk of noncommunicable disease⁶. It has previously been shown by many (including the APGC at JHI) that CEA offers the opportunity to manipulate, diversify and enhances the taste and nutritional value of fresh produce. Taste is major driver of repeat purchase (see earlier) and the proposed system offer the potential to grow high value desirable produce AND ensure that quality is maintained at every harvest.

Resilience

The UK eats around 450,000t of tomatoes a year and imports 385,000t of that. The Netherlands is the biggest source of imports, followed by Morocco and Spain. While the Dutch glasshouse industry is decarbonising, it still relies heavily on natural gas. In Spain and Morocco tomatoes do not rely on heat, but water shortages are likely to increase, and there are also longstanding concerns about labour practices⁷. The report on CEA by Savills (2019)⁸ identified that increasing domestic production of fresh produce through CEA systems has the potential to mitigate some of the UK's food security risk, while respecting the water security status of the exporting countries at the same time. Indeed, the water security risk in the countries we import from is identified (Fig. 5) and is projected to become much worse (Fig. 6⁹) since the report was published. Indeed, the recent report by the CBI entitled "What is the demand for fresh fruit and vegetables on the European market?"¹⁰ identifies a bleak picture for our current sources of imported fresh produce with the number of fruit and vegetable farms in Europe decreasing, and total production volume is not growing much at all. In the future, stagnating production volumes will create a need for external sources. This further support the opportunity for local production and greater fresh produce onshoring.

⁶ Increasing fruit and vegetable consumption to reduce the risk of noncommunicable diseases. 2023. WHO. <https://www.who.int/tools/elena/interventions/fruit-vegetables-ncds>; Madsen et al., 2023. Fruit and vegetable consumption and the risk of hypertension: a systematic review and meta-analysis of prospective studies. European Journal of Nutrition, pp.1-15.

⁷ <https://www.theguardian.com/global-development/2020/sep/20/we-pick-your-food-migrant-workers-speak-out-from-spains-plastic-sea>

⁸ CEA (2019) Savills Ltd. <https://pdf.euro.savills.co.uk/uk/rural---other/controlled-environment-agriculture.pdf>

⁹ EEA Climate change impacts in Europe.

<https://experience.arcgis.com/experience/5f6596de6c4445a58aec956532b9813d/>

¹⁰ CBI (2022) What is the demand for fresh fruit and vegetables on the European market?

[https://www.cbi.eu/market-information/fresh-fruit-vegetables/what-demand#:~:text=The%20number%20of%20fruit%20and,oranges%2C%20apples%20and%20tomatoes\).](https://www.cbi.eu/market-information/fresh-fruit-vegetables/what-demand#:~:text=The%20number%20of%20fruit%20and,oranges%2C%20apples%20and%20tomatoes).)

Fig. 5 Top 10 fruit and vegetable importers to the UK by value and water risk (Savills, 2019)

Fig. 6. Projected change in meteorological droughts for a medium emissions scenario (period 2041-2070, compared with 1981-2010). For the legend, the colours represent change in number of drought events per 30 years. (Taken from Climate change impacts in Europe, <https://tinyurl.com/4ujtf68k>)

Energy for production is, for CAE, a major influence of resilience. Scotland has numerous sources of renewable energy including - alongside wind, water and sun - landfill sites, disused coal mines, sewers and water treatment works, biogas plants etc. (see Scottish Parliament Information Centre¹¹). For CEA however the need for electricity and heating limits locational development. Allied to this is the associated costs of the energy specially if conversion is needed (heat to electricity, gas to heat etc) with the associated efficiency losses. The positioning at MSIP with access to both steam and electricity, via the MVV connection and wind turbines (4.2Mw), and the potential for long term off taker contract at sub grid prices. Allied to this is the possibility of developing the concept of low emission fresh produce production, a consequence of the energy sources: this feeds into the earlier identified drivers of fresh produce purchases.

¹¹) Scottish Parliament Information Centre 2023. Renewable energy map of Scotland. <https://spice-spotlight.scot/2023/05/18/renewable-energy-map-of-scotland/>

This project is intended to stimulate the wider development of the Scottish glasshouse sector. To our knowledge there is one commercial tomato grower in Scotland – Standhill Farm in the Scottish Borders with 4 acres in production. Another farmer in Dumfries and Galloway is about to go into production. Both are located on dairy farms and make use of methane from digesting cattle manure. Standhill also uses wood chips.

Markets

While most fresh produce and vegetables are sold through the multiple retailers, other routes to market include:

- Food service – hotels, restaurants, contract caterers
- Convenience stores and independent retailers
- Public procurement: between tomatoes, peppers and cucumbers Tayside Contracts buys around 50T/annum.
- Community food sector – small volumes but social and health benefits

Jobs

Employment if CEA systems are skilled jobs and with the advances in system control and automation can be operated with a small core of staff thereby providing secure employment and a diminishment in the need for unskilled labour. There is also the possibility that those with disabilities could be gainfully employed in such systems.

Training

Commercial reality is the aim for the potential CEA system at MSIP but if established this does offer the additional possibility of acting, to a degree, as a training centre for CEA and horticultural training beyond that offered by Dundee and Angus Colleges (DAC). APGC/JHI is in discussions with DAC around the revamping of their agri/horticultural offering via the Tay Cities Deal Life Sciences programme and this could fit aspects of that.

2 Key ingredients for success

The following are key criteria required for the realisation of the opportunity's potential

1. A solid business case identifying demand and price trends (for both fresh produce and plantlets depending on the variable business model)
2. Enterprise. Someone or some people who want to run the business.
3. Skills and sectoral experience.
4. Land – though not much compared to some other forms of farming. Typical yields of tomatoes are now around 60kg per square metre/600 tonnes per hectare. 5 hectares could grow all the fresh tomatoes eaten in Angus and Dundee. In principle, glasshouses can be built on top of other buildings such as warehouses and factory units, minimising footprint.
5. Reliable, affordable energy. Increasingly, UK glasshouses are being co-located with sources of renewable energy. At the MSIP immediate local level the arrangement offers opportunities to realise support via the exploitation of renewable energy as the heat source. This needs to be explored more fully. There are analogies for benefits to be explored with the discussion around equivalent energy costs support for electricity akin to red diesel in farming and field production.
6. Affordable capital.
7. Labour.
8. Marketing, packaging and distribution.
9. Customers. Here the possibility of council procurement raises possibilities.

3 Potential locations in Angus and Dundee

As this is a pre-feasibility assessment of the opportunity an extensive search of possible locations in Angus and Dundee has not been undertaken. Two possible sites were considered: the landfill site near Forfar and the Michelin Scotland Innovation Parc (MSIP) in Dundee.

The Forfar site has access to methane from a closed landfill site. This will continue to be produced although in diminishing quantities for a number of years. However, the volume produced is not sufficient for more than a small glasshouse. The Forfar site also has available land. However, heat and electricity and broadband infrastructure would be needed, as well as road access for deliveries and distribution.

MSIP enjoys many advantages over the Forfar site. There is a more energy available from the neighbouring MVV plant than is likely needed for the scale of the commercial CEA centre proposed. Furthermore, this would include the needs of a proposed vertical farm on site also that would offer both produce and plantlet production capabilities. This energy is available mostly as steam and electricity both is which can be used. The infrastructure to deliver steam and electricity is already in place. There are also wind turbines on site and the MVV energy-from-waste (EfW) plant is scheduled to operate for at least 24 years.

There is site security and HGV access, and the site itself is well-located for regional and national distribution. The presence of other hi-tech start-ups on site is also valuable possibly leading to innovation in CEA energy management developments such as energy storage for further efficiency gains, AI-enabled environmental management, packaging or processing, etc

There are also further synergies to be explored with the incineration plant.

Scottish Water are supportive of this Angus/Dundee project and keen to explore future possibilities, including using heat from sewers and energy from wastewater treatment. This sort of energy is already being used in SE England to grow tomatoes at scale¹².

Space available at MSIP

There is a 1.35ha steel-framed shed which could be stripped and glazed (Fig. 7) . Although, a feasibility needs to consider all options. Demolition of the shed and the new build of a CEA systems (glasshouse and/or vertical farm) offers many benefits in terms of height and therefore energy/productivity efficiency.

A further 6.45 hectares (64,500 m²) of undeveloped land is available within the site and zoned for industrial development, and can be seen in Fig. 8 from the MVV plant

- Land is currently zoned for Class 4, 5, 6 activities ([The Town and Country Planning \(Use Classes\) \(Scotland\) Order 1997 \(legislation.gov.uk\)](#))
- Land does not have services at present however options exist to provide connection to both steam and power from the energy from waste facility.
- Road access could either be via MSIP or directly to Drumgeith Road to the north.
- Energy provision from the MVV efW plant is identified in Fig 9.

¹² <https://www.cibsejournal.com/case-studies/growing-interest-using-wastewater-to-heat-britains-giant-greenhouses/>

Fig. 7. Available space at MSIP for the siting of a CEA system for fresh produce and plantlet production

Fig 8. Underdeveloped land at MSIP possible available for expansion of the CEA system development

- Existing steam pipeline from MEB energy from waste facility
- Potential tie in point for additional steam offtake
- Existing unused private wire HV (11kV – 6MW) connection from MEB energy from waste facility

Fig 9. The layout of the site with respect to energy provision from the MVV EfW plant

4 Possible business model

As identified above this needs to be developed from a commercial perspective with the other potential benefits/outcomes of training opportunities, social/societal impacts etc explored once a viable CEA system has been established.

Different models for ownership and operation are possible.

- The energy provider runs the glasshouse directly.
- The fresh produce producer (or consortium thereof) invests in the glasshouse and buys the power.
- A public body, or special purpose vehicle, to make the initial capital investment and lease the glasshouses on a profit-sharing arrangement to a vegetable producer, who would pay for energy and other services.
- The producer could be an existing fresh produce grower (national/international) wanting to expand, or a field/polytunnel fresh produce producer already used to operating at a commercial scale.

If the latter, it would be important to hire external expertise for a start-up period.

The lease could include provision for supplying Tayside contracts and/or local social enterprises with produce. Preliminary discussion with Dundee Council have, to date, proven friendly and welcoming and this is encouraging as they will have role to play in terms of planning, zoning, support and potentially as an off-taker of produce via food procurement for the to-be-established owner/operator.

5 Possible add-ons

Vertical farm

Vertical farms differ from conventional glasshouses in that they do not rely at all on natural light, using artificial light to grow plants in stacks. This allows very high levels of production of herbs, salads and other fast-growing crops.

A vertical farm on site at MSIP could complement the conventional glasshouse, and there might be some benefits of shared infrastructure.

As well as growing food crops, vertical farms are well-suited to growing plugs – including the tomato, pepper and cucumber plants for the glasshouses. Potentially, a vertical farm could

also grow brassica and strawberry transplants for the fruit and veg sector in Tayside.

The James Hutton Institute has established the Advanced Plant Growth Centre at Invergowrie and some of the know-how being developed (for example on using light more ingeniously) would benefit the glasshouses.

CO₂ capture

The MVV plant emits carbon dioxide which could be captured (cleaned if necessary to remove nitrogen and sulphur based contaminants) and used in the glasshouses to enrich the atmosphere and promote plant growth : impact on yield and quality could be x1.5-3.

Circular economy

Nitrous oxides produced by the MVV plant (and subsequently scrubbed so they don't go into the atmosphere) could in theory be recycled to provide plant fertiliser. This is an area that could involve existing MSIP residents or even attract new ones with innovation potential for the sector. Similarly, nitrogen and phosphorous could in principle be recycled at water treatment works.

Valorisation of the biomass waste from the CEA system could be used as sustainable feedstocks for fresh produces packaging.

Community food production

A small (say 0.1ha) section of one glasshouse could be made available to a local community food organisation to produce a range of fruit and vegetables, similar to the development at Camperdown. Being able to grow in the winter can also help with people's mental health. As stated above this needs to follow the establishment of a viable business. This approach would generate significant positive feedback and could likely be supported by the plethora of support, charity and funding schemes available

Café/visitor centre

The produce generated could feed into the new MSIP Innovation hub café and/or via direct sales to the site residents.

6 Aspects to be defined.

Site acquisition/leasing costs

- Likelihood of developing the greenfield site with another business so the glasshouse can be on the rooftop?¹³
- Construction costs – for the greenfield site, likely to be in the region of £10m for 4 hectares, £15m for 6 hectares. For converting or demolishing-and -rebuild the 1.35ha shed – TBD.
- Feasibility of using hot water from the plant – this heat is currently not used and is available in high volumes but is not as hot as in typical systems. What adaptations would be needed?
- Costs of energy from the plant - specifically electricity for lighting, including at night, and and HVAC.
- Other input cost implications
- Energy contract duration would impact the attractiveness of the opportunity to investors.
- Where might the capital come from? Predicated on a fuller detailing of the opportunity, SWOT and cost/benefit analysis,
- Would night running be viewed as light pollution? The site is in an urban area.

7 A budget with gaps

A very preliminary attempt at cost/benefit has been drafted.

Glasshouse budget with gaps

Assumptions:

total of 6ha in production

100% tomatoes (for simplicity; in practice probably peppers and cucumbers and aubergines)

farmgate price £1300/t average over year - this is average for 2018-2022 five year period)

marketable yield 50kg/m² (conservative)

Income

3000t tomatoes at £1300 **3,900,000**

Expenditure

Labour	30%	1,170,000
Energy	10%	390,000
Plants	?120,000	120,000
water	c. 12m litres	
CO2	?2000t	200,000
Nutrients	10%?	390,000
bees, other	5%?	195,000
Packaging	?5%	195,000
Rental	say 5% of £15m	750,000

total **3,410,000**

Profit 490,000

¹³ <https://www.dezeen.com/2022/02/04/rooftop-greenhouse-agrotopia-urban-agriculture-architecture-belgium/>

8 Next steps

A full feasibility study is required to provide answers and options for the issues identified above. The cost of this would probably be in the region of £50-100,000. The APGC/JHI is prepared to be the lead organisation for this.

The project would benefit from a co-operative approach from the key stakeholders – Angus and Dundee Councils, MSIP and MVV, along with Scottish Government, James Hutton Institute, and the many fresh produce grower companies already engaged at the meetings to date. Scottish Water are also keen to be involved in wider discussions about other future sites and opportunities. Stakeholders could form an Operational Group to take the project forward and act as the client for the feasibility study.